

MENSTRUAL IRREGULARITIES IN OBESE GIRLS

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Annotation. Obesity is a non-communicable pandemic and a major problem worldwide. As the prevalence of childhood obesity increases, there is growing evidence of a link between obesity and risk factors for menstrual irregularities.

Keywords. Obesity in adolescents, menstrual cycle disorders.

Аннотация. Ожирение носит характер неинфекционной пандемии и является серьезной проблемой во всем мире. По мере увеличения распространенности детского ожирения появляется все больше доказательств связи между ожирением и факторами риска нарушений менструального цикла.

Ключевые слова. Ожирение у подростков, нарушения менструального цикла.

Izoh. Semizlik yuqumli bo'lmagan pandemiya bo'lib, butun dunyo bo'ylab jiddiy muammo hisoblanadi. Bolalarda semirishning tarqalishi ortib borayotganligi sababli, semirish va hayz davrining buzilishi uchun xavf omillari o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik haqida dalillar kuchaymoqda.

Kalit so'zlar. O'smirlarda semirish, hayz davrining buzilishi.

Relevance. Obesity in the younger generation is currently one of the most pressing medical and social problems in the modern world, but it is little covered and is becoming more and more threatening. In recent decades, the world has seen a trend towards a rapid increase in the number of children and adolescents with obesity. Excess body weight and obesity have become one of the most common endocrine disorders in children and adolescents, among schoolchildren, the frequency of lipid metabolism disorders currently reaches 25-30%.

The purpose of this study. To study the effect of non-drug therapy for obesity on the characteristics of the menstrual cycle in adolescent girls.

Materials and methods of research. The basis for the formation of menstrual cycle disorders in overweight girls is a violation of gonadotropin secretion, insulin resistance (IR) and hyperinsulinemia, which over time lead to hyperandrogenism. A decrease in the level of somatotrophic hormone, insulin-like growth factor and an increase in the level of leptin lead to a violation of the correct functioning of the hypothalamic-pituitary system. These changes can explain the violations of ovulatory function and, consequently, the reproductive health of adolescents. The onset of puberty in girls occurs at the age of 8-9 years and depends on many factors, including heredity, nutritional characteristics and physical activity. The average age of menarche in Uzbekistan is 13-14 years, but in adolescent girls with excess body weight, puberty begins earlier than in girls with normal body weight, possibly isolated thelarche, menarche occurs earlier.

Studies show that in obese adolescent girls aged 11–15 years, sexual development is characterized by early onset (on average, at 10.8 ± 0.8 years), the average height is 171 ± 3 cm, BMI is from 31.2 to 43 kg/m² (on average, 37.1 ± 5.9 kg/m²). The age of menarche is from 9.9 to 13.5 years. Menstrual cycle disorders were detected in 70% of the examined girls, most

often (60%) of the oligomenorrhea type. The proportion of patients with secondary amenorrhea and acyclic uterine bleeding during puberty is the same (20% and 20%, respectively). In addition, in overweight girls, deviations in the order of appearance of sexual characteristics are observed: the frequency of isolated pubarche is 33%, while in the population this figure is 15%. The endocrine basis for the untimely manifestation of sexual hair growth is excessive adrenarche.

Conclusion. Dynamic changes in body weight can have both positive and negative effects on the prognosis of menstrual cycle disorders, which determines the great importance of therapeutic efforts aimed at reducing body weight.

Overweight and obesity in adolescence not only affect appearance and lead to the development of many diseases, but also have a detrimental effect on the proper functioning of the entire reproductive system, which cannot but affect the health of a woman in adulthood. Obesity in childhood increases the likelihood of overweight or obesity in adulthood, disability or premature death. In addition to problems with the regularity of the menstrual cycle, teenage girls with obesity may suffer from hypertension, shortness of breath, are limited in their physical activity and often experience psychological problems.

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